

Infrared Spectra, Magnetic Susceptibility and Electronic Spectra as Aids in the Study of Structure and Bonding of the Hexamethyl phosphoramidate Adducts of Some Dioxouranium (VI) Salts

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The complexes of the types $[\text{UO}_2\text{X}_2(\text{HMPA})_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3$ and NCS and $\text{HMPA} =$ hexamethyl phosphoramidate) and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2(\text{HMPA})_3]$ have been thoroughly characterized by the i.r. spectra, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra. It has been found that the asymmetric stretching frequency (ν_3) and χ_M (the molar magnetic susceptibility) of the dioxouranium (VI) ion depend in a more or less similar extent on the donor ability of the anionic ligands towards the uranyl (VI) ion—a typical hard acid. The electronic spectra in the visible region of all the complexes which are originated due to oxygen \rightarrow uranium charge transfer and are essentially the $T \leftarrow S$ transition are found to be very much sensitive to the equatorial (secondary) ligands. It has also been found that the complexes where equatorial coordination numbers are greater than four, do not absorb below $20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band of hexamethyl phosphoramidate undergoes unusual blue shift in going from a nonpolar to a polar solvent and a probable reasoning is incorporated. The effect of coordination on this $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band of the pure phosphoramidate has also been discussed.

In a previous communication¹ we have described the isolation and characterization of some hexamethyl phosphoramidate adducts of dioxouranium (VI) and uranium (IV) salts. These complexes undergo 'acid solvolysis' in methanol and acetonitrile, and are practically non-electrolyte in dichloromethane. Details of the solvolytic equilibria that exist in the two solvents and evaluation of the equilibrium constants have also been attempted by us². Herein is reported a thorough characterization of the dioxouranium (VI) complexes by a study of their infrared bands with special reference to the effect of the secondary ligands³ on the multiplicity of the U-O bond. Since the UO_2^{2+} ion is slightly paramagnetic owing to the large f -orbital contribution⁴ in its formation ($O 2p\pi \rightarrow U 5f\pi$) and since the extent of donor ability of the secondary ligands is supposed to have a profound effect on the said dative overlap, and as such on the involvement of uranium $5f$ orbitals in bond formation, the change in values of the molar magnetic susceptibility (χ_M) of the uranyl (VI) ion should also be dependent on the donor ability of the secondary ligands (cf. results and discussion). So, the force constants of the U-O bond in the oxocation is compared with the χ_M of the said ion, in the present work, to arrive at a reasonable conclusion regarding the above hypothesis. The electronic spectra of the complexes in different solvents, viz., in dichloromethane (where mainly the unsolvolyzed species occur), in acetonitrile and methanol (where different solvolysis products are there) are recorded

and by Gaussian Analyses and the calculation of oscillator strengths it has been revealed that: (1) the normally spin forbidden transitions are sufficiently allowed due to strong spin-orbit coupling, (2) the structured features of the uranyl spectra are sensitive to equatorial ligands and (3) the equatorial coordination numbers have profound effect on the uranyl absorption, specially in the longer wavelength range.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectral bands of the ligand hexamethyl phosphoramidate and the complexes formed of it are qualitatively assigned in Table I, wherefrom it is found that the original P-O band^{5,6} of the free ligand (1198 cm^{-1}) is slightly lowered in the complexes ($5-20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This small red shift can be accounted for if it is assumed that (a) in the absence of any effect on the P-O bond due to coordination the P-O stretching frequency ought to be raised by coupling with the M-O bond, (b) the inductive effect of coordination will strengthen the P-O σ -bond but weaken the P-O π -bond and (c) since the P-O frequency is experimentally found to be lowered, the inductive effect on the P-O π -bond is the predominating feature. But in this case the P=O vibrational frequencies are not drastically lowered on complexation like the corresponding phosphine oxide complexes⁷. The relay effect in the phosphoramidate due to the presence of a large number of electron repelling methyl groups is so pronounced that the weakening of P-O π -bond cannot drastically affect the P-O bond order. The sharp bands found in the regions 1162 and 1290 cm^{-1} are mentioned to

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be the components of P-N and C-N bands due to $P-N <_c$ skeleton⁸ and this has been referred to as balancing vibration, R_{Me} . The absence of any band in the region $650-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ where P-N band occurs in the case of trivalent phosphorus⁸ and observation of a characteristic strong band in the $740-758\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the pure hexamethyl phosphoramide as well as in the complexes ensure this to be due to pentavalent phosphorus-nitrogen vibration⁸. The nitrate groups function as bidentate ligand¹ and the thiocyanate groups are coordinated through hard nitrogen end in the corresponding complexes and in the complex, $UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 2HMPA$ the thiocyanate probably functions as a bridging group involving only the nitrogen end, as we have reported in our preliminary communication¹. In the complex $[UO_2(HMPA)_5](ClO_4)_2$ the $\bar{\nu}_3$ of ClO_4^- is observed as a broad band at $1060-1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region characteristic of T_d symmetry of the said group⁹.

In all the complexes $\bar{\nu}_3$ of the uranyl ion is observed in the region $916-932\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\bar{\nu}_1$ is always unobserved suggesting thereby that UO_2^{2+} is possibly linear (D_∞ symmetry) in the complexes¹⁰. This $\bar{\nu}_3$ is found to be quite sensitive towards equatorial ligands and the said asymmetric stretching frequency in the present case increases in ligand order, $HMPA < Cl^- \sim NCS^-$ (tris ligated) $< NCS^-$ (bis-ligated) $< Br^- < NO_3^-$. This is a reverse order of the electron donating ability of anionic nucleophiles towards the UO_2^{2+} ion—a 'special type' of hard acid¹¹ as this ordering is quite consistent since the existing idea on the structure of the uranyl (VI) ion^{3,12} entails that the 'extradative bond' formation in the said oxocation is impaired as the secondary ligands become more and more potential electron donors. In this connection it may be mentioned that the similar ordering of anionic ligands obtained by Majumdar and Bhattacharyya³ in the cases of the quinoline N-oxide adducts of dioxouranium (VI) salts was slightly different, viz., $NCS^- < C^- < NO_3^- \sim Br^-$. So, it could be said that when organic ligands are different, straightforward comparison regarding the trend of the change of $\bar{\nu}_3$ of the UO_2^{2+} ion with the change of anionic ligands is difficult, since apart from the electronic interactions of these ligands, vibrational interactions of Jones¹⁰ would be operative leading the resultant effect unpredictable.

Magnetic susceptibility :

The small paramagnetic susceptibility of the uranyl (VI) ion observed in the complexes (table 2) in spite of its possessing a totally symmetric singlet ground state has been ascribed⁴ to the large orbital contribution due to the involvement of uranium $5f$ electrons in forming the said ion. The largest contribution coming from the two $5f \sigma$ -bonding electrons is calculated from the relation $16N \alpha \beta^2 / \Delta$, where N is the Avogadro number, β is the Bohr Magneton, α is the probability that the bonding electron is in the uranium $5f$ states (as opposed to its being located on an oxygen atom) and the Δ is the energy required

to promote a $5f \sigma$ -bonding electron to a $5f \pi$ state. So, it is clear that the susceptibility is directly proportional to α and α in its turn depends on "extradative bond formation" and ultimately on the multiplicity of the U-O bond. Since the multiplicity of the said bond is dependent on the donor ability of the equatorial ligands and also since one such ligand, HMPA, is fixed, the χ_A of UO_2^{2+} ion would naturally depend on the donor ability of the anionic nucleophiles and this χ_A would parallel with the force constant of the U-O bond. It is actually apparent from table 2 that within the limits of the experimental error, the two parameters, the stretching force constant of U-O bond in the uranyl ion (K_{eff}) and the χ_A of the said ion depend in the same fashion on the nature of the secondary ligands.

The electronic spectra :

An examination of the electronic spectra of the isolated complexes in different solvents reveals the following features :

- transitions within the UO_2^{2+} ion,
 - secondary ligands $\rightarrow UO_2^{2+}$ charge transfer,
- and (c) intraligand transitions of the organic ligand molecules.

The salient observations and their interpretations are outlined as follows :

- The uranyl spectrum in the region $350-520\text{ nm}$ is due to coupling of several vibrational frequencies of the complex, principally the symmetrical O-U-O frequencies, to several closely spaced very weak T \leftarrow S electron transfer transition¹³. The spin selection rule has been broken down due to spin orbit coupling. The band positions and their intensities of the different uranyl (VI) complexes as studied in three non-aqueous solvents, viz., dichloromethane, acetonitrile and methanol suggest that the bands are quite sensitive to the equatorial ligations as also to the solvents. The dichloromethane solution actually represents the true spectra of the unsolvolyzed species but, as we have reported², in methanol and acetonitrile acid solvolysis occurs and different solvolyzed species prevail in those solutions along with a considerable amount of unsolvolyzed species. So, only the spectra of the complexes in dichloromethane solvent are shown in Fig. 1 and to emphasize clearly that the 'structured features' of the uranyl spectra are dependent on the equatorial ligands, as also on the solvent medium the spectra of the chloro complex in acetonitrile and methanol are also shown in Fig. 2. The regions, viz., $27,000-18,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ within which all the absorption maxima due to UO_2^{2+} group are observed in the present cases [excepting Br^- and NCS^- complexes where the bands are observable only upto $24,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ because of the reducible nature of the anionic ligands and as such the (Br^- , SCN^-) $\rightarrow UO_2^{2+}$ charge transfer encroached within the uranyl region] is the triplet multiplet region, perturbed by being mixed with the perturbing singlets of higher energy¹³. From the data it appears that

TABLE I—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF HMPA AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH UO_2^{2+} SALTS

Compound	Frequencies(cm^{-1})									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
HMPA	750(s)	—	980(s)	1062(s)	1162(sh) 1290(s)	1198(s)	1480(sh)	2805(sh)	—	—
$UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2HMPA$	758(vs) 768(sh)	920(vs)	988-1000 (vs,b)	1084(vs)	1100(sh) 1298(vs)	1186(s)	1480(sh)	2825(sh)	—	—
$UO_2Br_2 \cdot 2HMPA$	758(vs)	925(vs)	980-1008 (vs,b)	1062-1095 (vs,b)	1104(sh) 1298(vs)	1188(vs)	1450(s) 1468(s) 1480(sh)	2825(sh)	—	—
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2HMPA$	758(sh) 764(sh)	932(vs)	990(vs) 1004(sh)	1070(sh)	1092-1110 (vs,b) 1298(sh)	1190(vs)	1454(sh)	2860(sh)	1500(vs) $\bar{\nu}_1$ 1032(m) $\bar{\nu}_2$ 748(s) $\bar{\nu}_3$ 1286(vs) $\bar{\nu}_4$ 728(sh) $\bar{\nu}_5$ 815(w) $\bar{\nu}_6$	—
$UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 2HMPA$	756(sh) 764(vs)	922(vs)	990-1004 (vs,b)	1074(s) 1115(s)D	1170(sh) 1305(s)	1192(s)	1455(s)D 1470(s) 1482(sh)	2860(s)	—	2045(vs) 2080(vs)D 2125(sh)
$UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 3HMPA$	758(vs)	920(vs)	988-1004 (vs,b)	1072(sh) 1088(vs) 1125(vs)	1165(sh) 1306(vs)	1190(s)	1470(s) 1480(sh)	2870(sh)	—	2080(vs)
$UO_2(HMPA)_5(ClO_4)_2$	782(w)	916(w)	992(w)	—	—	1160(w)	1480(s)	2870(s)	1060-1100 $\bar{\nu}(s,b)$ $+\bar{\nu}(C-N)$ Assym. + $\bar{\nu}(P-N < C)$ skeleton	—

1. P-N vibration for pentavalent phosphates⁸. 2. $\bar{\nu}_3$ (U = O)¹⁰. 3. Sym. C-N vib.⁸. 4. Assym. C-N vib.⁸. 5. Further component of C-N and P-N frequency due to P-N < C skeleton⁸. 6. $\bar{\nu}$ (P = O)^{9,10}. 7. Assym. C-H def.⁸. 8. $\bar{\nu}$ (C-H) characteristic of the Me₂N group⁸. 9. Vibration modes of NO₃ group ($\bar{\nu}_1$ to $\bar{\nu}_6$)^{11,12,13}. 10. C = N stretch of N bonded thiocyanate¹.

probably two components of the T ← S bands are found each for of the complex (excepting the bromo and thiocyanato complexes where probably one is observed) having no other component of the triplet multiplet according to the energy level diagram of the UO_2^{2+} ion¹³. The other possible components of the perturbed triplets and the transitions $\text{S}^* \leftarrow \text{S}$, the perturbing singlets are all hidden within the very

intense, high energy visible and U.V. bands due to charge transfer (ligand → UO_2^{2+}) and due to the intraligand (organic) transitions. Now, the observed

sensitivities of the UO_2^{2+} spectra and of the $\bar{\nu}_3$ of the UO_2^{2+} ion towards the equatorial ligands indicate that the equatorial coordination set may be slightly staggered and a contribution from the uranium orbitals which have no electron density normal to the z-axis (internuclear axis containing equatorial plane) viz., f_{xyz} , f_{zx^2} , f_{z^3} , d_{xz} and d_{yz} , are also involved to some extent in bonding with the equatorial ligands¹⁴. This supposition is needed because the UO_2^{2+} ion being a typical hard acid is incapable of forming any equatorial π bond.

TABLE 2—CORRELATION OF MOLAR MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND THE STRETCHING FORCE CONSTANT OF THE UO_2^{2+} ION IN THE COMPLEXES.

Compound	χ_M of UO_2^{2+} $\times 10^6$ e.m.u.	K_{eff} in mdynes/Å° of U = O bond calculated from the observed $\bar{\nu}_3$ of the UO_2^{2+} ion
$\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	83	7.50
$\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	115	7.58
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	118	7.69
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	100	7.53
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 3\text{HMPA}$	87	7.50
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{HMPA})_5](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	46	7.43

Some features of the uranyl spectrum deserve special mention. The complex where the equatorial coordination number is six (total 8 coordination including two oxide ligands), viz., the nitrate complex, $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ which is characterized by two short-bite bidentate nitrate ligands¹ does not absorb below 20,000 cm^{-1} and this observation is in agreement with the previous work¹⁵ about the uranyl spectra. The spectra in dichloromethane where the solvation is practically nil, show that only the complex $\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ absorbs below 20,000 cm^{-1} and so we might suggest that in this complex possibly uranium has the equatorial coordination number of four¹⁵. The complex $\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ which also does not absorb below 20,000 cm^{-1} contains bridging thiocyanate ligand¹, and since the chloro complex, $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$, again does not absorb below the said wave number region, may therefore contain bridging chloride group as well, so that the equatorial coordination number of uranium in both the cases becomes more than four. Though in the complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{HMPA})_5](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, in all probability, the uranium atom has equatorial coordination number of 5, its reflectance spectrum shows band below 20,000 cm^{-1} .

(b) The bands corresponding to the low energy region (42,000–30,000 cm^{-1}) of the UV absorption spectra of HMPA and the uranyl (VI) complexes have probably been originated from secondary ligand → UO_2^{2+} charge transfer, as the molar extinction coefficients, ϵ_{max} , are quite high and the HMPA itself does not show any such absorption band in this region. Of course the molar extinction of the absorption band in cyclohexane could not be assessed since the complexes being sparingly soluble in the said solvent, the suspended solids were shaken with the cyclohexane solvent for nearly twenty four hours and from the filtrate obtained, the absorptions were measured. It is found (Table 3) that the spectral bands in this region are better resolved in cyclohexane than in methanol. In spite of the extensive acid solvolysis reaction of the complexes operative in methanol², the UV spectra of the individual complex are sometimes quite different from the other. This indicates that at even such a high dilution (Table 3) some amount of undissociated species still remains.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra in dichloromethane solution of (A) $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$, (B) $\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$, (C) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ (cell thickness 2 cm. each), (D) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ and (E) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 3\text{HMPA}$ (cell thickness 1 cm.).

TABLE 3—ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF HMPA AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH UO_2^{2+} SALTS IN CYCLOHEXANE AND METHANOL IN THE RANGE OF 42,000–30,000 cm_2^{-1}

Compound	In cyclohexane		In methanol	
	Band position in cm^{-1}	log ϵ	Band position in cm^{-1}	log ϵ
HMPA	None	—	None	—
$\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ *($1.831 \times 10^{-4} M$) in case of methanol)	40,000(sh) 39,682–38,169(B) 37,314(sh) 36,231(sh) 35,714 34,722 32,468	— — — — — — —	41,666 39,682 35,714–33,334	3.50 3.46 3.15
$\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ *($1.828 \times 10^{-4} M$) in case of methanol)	39,682(sh) 38,760 37,879 37,037 35,460 34,346(sh)	— — — — — —	42,372 41,318 40,650 39,062(sh) 32,258–30,303(B)	3.47 3.47 3.46 — 2.98
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ *($1.968 \times 10^{-4} M$) in case of methanol)	40,322(sh) 39,682 38,760 37,037 32,680	— — — — —	40,000(sh) 39,062(sh) 36,231 31,847 31,250	— — 3.20 2.94 2.91
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ *($2.204 \times 10^{-4} M$) in case of methanol)	41,318 40,650 39,370(sh) 35,460 34,964 33,784	— — — — — —	35,714–32,258(B) 31,250	3.39 3.34
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 3\text{HMPA}$ *($9.101 \times 10^{-5} M$) in case of methanol)	38,760(sh) 35,971(sh) 34,964 34,482(sh)	— — — —	39,062(sh) 34,482–32,258(B)	— 3.28

sh = shoulder, B = broad

* Figures within the brackets indicate the respective molar concentration.

 Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$ in (A) methanol (cell thickness 1 cm.), and (B) acetonitrile (cell thickness 2 cm.).

(c) By measuring the spectra in the high energy UV region (220–232 nm) in cyclohexane and methanol it has been found that the ligand HMPA shows a strong absorption band at 226 nm (44.25 kK) in the former and at 232 nm (43.10 kK) in the latter solvent with $\log \epsilon$ values of 2.27 and 1.97 respectively (Table 4).

TABLE 4—ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF HMPA AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH UO_2^{2+} SALT IN CYCLOHEXANE AND METHANOL IN THE RANGE OF 45,450–43,480 cm^{-1}

Compound	In cyclohexane		In methanol	
	Band position in cm^{-1}	$\log \epsilon$	Band position in cm^{-1}	$\log \epsilon$
HMPA	44,247	2.27	45,045	1.97
$\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	45,249	—	Above 45,450	—
$\text{UO}_2\text{Br}_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	45,249	—	—	—
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	45,045	—	—	—
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 2\text{HMPA}$	45,249	—	—	—
$\text{UO}_2(\text{NCS})_2\cdot 3\text{HMPA}$	45,249	—	—	—

This type of hypsochromic shift of 4 nm in going from cyclohexane to methanol solvent with hypsochromic effect is consistent with the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition¹⁶ in the organic chromophore. But this same band suffers blue shift in each of the solvents on complexation of the ligand with uranyl (VI) salts. In cyclohexane the extent of the blue shift is almost 4–5 nm and in methanol solvent, the profile of each curve clearly shows the band position to lie beyond 220 nm in the lower wavelength region. However, this type of blue shift of the band after complexation suggests the coordination of the ligand phosphoramidate to the uranium atom through oxygen. But it is also expected that the band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition should disappear after complex formation by donation of the non-bonding (lone pair) $2p$ electrons of the oxygen atom of the phosphoramidate. So, the said band may be attributed to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition within the phosphoramidate and the bands very naturally undergo blue shift after complexation with the UO_2^{2+} ion. The unusual blue shift of the absorption band of the pure phosphoramidate in going from cyclohexane to methanol is probably due to the highly polar nature of both solvent and solute producing a negative solvation energy for the Franck-Condon state¹⁷ of the phosphoramidate molecule.

Experimental

Solvent purifications :

The G.R. (E.Merck) quality methanol, cyclohexane and dichloromethane were distilled before use. Acetonitrile (extra pure Riedel) was treated with P_2O_5 , kept for 2 days and then distilled and the process was repeated until further addition of P_2O_5 did not impart any yellow colouration to the latter. The middle fractions of the solvents so purified were used for absorption measurements.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra were studied in Nujol mulls and recorded on Perkin-Elmer's 'Infracord' equipped with rock-salt optics. The chart papers were calibrated with recommended polystyrene bands.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant. A semimicro balance having uncertainties of 0.02 mg was used for weighing purpose and the whole arrangement was as recommended¹⁸ for measurement of susceptibility at room temperature. Diamagnetic corrections for ligand atoms and ions were made using Pascal's constant values^{18–20}. So, the maximum errors introduced in χ_M values are $\pm 10 \times 10^{-6}$ units which though alter the absolute values of χ_M to a certain extent but the relative ordering remains practically the same and it is this ordering which is important in the present case. The values of χ_M reported here are the mean values calculated by averaging the same obtained by three independent measurements.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra were measured in Hilger U.V. spectrophotometer in the visible range using glass cells and in the U.V. region using quartz cells. In case of the complex for which no suitable solvent could be found, its reflectance spectrum in the solid state was measured with an Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, attached with reflectance arrangement using MgCO_3 as a standard.

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